

Systematic review on valuation uptake

Criteria for the screening of papers

While 'experts'(Yann, Cem, David) only screened papers based on title and abstract, this was a proxy for criteria reviewers would apply to the full text of the study. Therefore I suggest applying the exclusion/screen out rules below to (i) abstract, title, keywords and (ii) full text when available.

RULE D1: A valuation application is in a specific location. Papers containing place names are more likely to be an application, but this criterium is not absolute, it just increases probability, in combination with rules below. Reviewers would have been likely to screen a study out as "not ES/NCP, not valuation" if there is no "study area" mentioned in the paper as a whole

Coding interpretation D1.1: screen out if no "study area" , "study site" , or synonym or <capitalized propername>

RULE D2: "NOT (a valuation paper of ES/NCP that assesses the importance of nature and ES to people or human-nature relationships)" (from the protocol used by the reviewers):

Valuation Uptake Review_classification_&_definitions.docx

Coding Interpretation D2.1: screen out if no mention of "human", "people", "stakeholder*" or synonyms

RULE D3: With reference to the Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response framework. A study quantifying D-P-S linkages is not ES/NCP because it does not quantify the Impact/Importance for, or Responses by humans. "Human-nature relationships" refer to the relationship between State-Impact-Response indicators.

Ecological function between two non-human species or a state not identified as a service or benefit in the ecosystem service cascade framework. Natural science that assessed relationships between pressure and state variables often use a chemical substance or non-human species name in latin in title or abstract, rather than a popular name.

Coding Interpretation D3.1: screen out studies without non-human species names in latin (use a substance library), chemical substances (use a species library for terms)

RULE Y1: from title: rule out papers with obviously irrelevant topics such as medical papers...; for titles that only refer to bio-physical assessments or notions, go to abstract and rule 3 below.

Coding Interpretation Y1.1: screen out papers with pharmaceutical compound and medical diagnosis terminology (use a substance library) in the title, abstract or keywords

RULE Y2: From title: rule in papers that explicitly address ecosystem services valuation; ecosystem assessments; economic analysis (cost-benefit analysis...) AND some environmental topic in a wide sense; rule out papers that don't.

Coding Interpretation Y2.1: do NOT screen out IF "ecosystem service", "valuation", "ecosystem assessment", "economic analysis", "cost", "benefit, "impact" , "environment*" IN the title

RULE Y3.1: From abstract: rule in papers that address bio-physical assessments with an indication of a policy-making role (e.g. support planning).

Comment: could be captured with a sufficient condition for screening in focusing on the title only

Coding Interpretation Y3.1.1: IF TS=12 keywords (defined in the corpus protocol) appear in the title do NOT screen out

RULE Y3.2: Rule out papers that do not seem to have an application (e.g. technical papers) or an environmental policy implication (in a broad sense).

Coding Interpretation Y3.2.1: use rule D1.1

RULE Y3.3: Rule out papers that do not seem to have an environmental policy implication (in a broad sense).

Coding Interpretation Y3.3.1: use rule Y3.1.1

Aidin Notes:

Applying the rules, except D3-1 and Y1-1 to the studies screened for review

To further proceed with the evaluation of rules:

1. The list of studies that screened out for review
2. A proper link between corpus and the screened dataset